

Synthesis and spectral investigations of the complex of $S_3N_3Cl_3$ with zinc(II)

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The complex of $S_3N_3Cl_3$ with ZnO has been synthesised and analysed by mass, IR, electronic and EPR spectra and assigned as $[S_3N_3Cl_3]_3 \cdot ZnO$. The complex is found to be paramagnetic in character, having S-Cl \rightarrow Zn coordination, distorted tetrahedral geometrical array and $4sp^3$ hybridization.

The formation of the ionic complexes of $S_3N_3Cl_3$ with Al and Mo have been reported^{1,2}. But the complexes of trithiazyltrichloride (TTTC), $S_3N_3Cl_3$ with Cu, Th and Zr synthesised, have been found to be the coordinated and metal bridged complexes³⁻⁵. In continuation, the investigations of the complex of $S_3N_3Cl_3$ with ZnO, prepared, are being presented herewith.

Results and discussion

The complex of $S_3N_3Cl_3$ with ZnO, which is cream coloured and soluble only in NH_4OH and CH_3COOH , decomposes on heating above 360° .

The analytical data of the complex % found, (calcd.) S 35.20 (35.32), N 15.40 (15.45), Cl 39.01 (39.18), Zn 7.97 (8.01), O 1.94 (1.96) and mol. wt. 819.56 (815.0) $g\ mol^{-1}$, lead to formulate it as $[S_3N_3Cl_3]_3 \cdot ZnO$, which is also supported by its mass spectrum. The mass lines (m/z ratio, Table 1), 107, 242, 487, and 570 are according to 3 Cl atom, $S_3N_3Cl_3$ ring, $(S_3N_3Cl_3)_2$ dimer and $[S_3N_3Cl_3]_2 \cdot ZnO$ fragments of the complex. The appearance of mass line at 605 m/z for $[S_3N_3Cl_3]_2 \cdot ZnO-Cl$, indicates the presence of third $S_3N_3Cl_3$ ring of which one Cl atom has linked to $[S_3N_3Cl_3]_2 \cdot ZnO$ group in the complex, as assigned by its molecular

formula.

IR spectral analysis : In the IR spectrum (Table 1) of the complex the vibrations observed are on account of S-Cl, S-Cl \rightarrow Zn S-N ring, and N-S-Cl bands, explaining that TTTC has coordinated to ZnO through its Cl atom (free S-Cl band found at $417\ cm^{-1}$). S and N atoms of TTTC ring have not coordinated, if it has happened, the frequencies in its IR spectrum should appear in the range of $500-700\ cm^{-1}$. The peak at $728\ cm^{-1}$ is due to the presence of S-N ring. The values, calculated, for the force constants show the presence of alternative single and double bonds in the ring with its coordination to ZnO.

Electronic and EPR spectra : Two peaks at 200 and 218 nm, out of which the former is due to charge transfer transition, caused by Zn^{2+} ions, while latter vibration is for $p\pi-d\pi$ transition of $S_3N_3Cl_3$ ring, are observed in the electronic spectrum of the complex and after that, the spectrum remains unchanged inferring coordination of $S_3N_3Cl_3$ ring to ZnO with complexion. This view is also supported by the values of oscillator strength f of order of 10^{-4} for the spin allowed Laporte forbidden transition but with $d\pi-p\pi$ mixing⁶ (T_d -symmetry). The low values of band gap energies ($\Delta E = 1.46, 1.204$) and high value of No. of conducting

Table 1. Mass and IR spectral data of the complex

Mass		IR Parameters		
m/z ratio	Bands assigned	Vibrations cm^{-1}	Bands assigned	$K \times 10^5$ $dyns/cm^{-2}$
107	3Cl	428.57	S-Cl	-
120	(N-S-N) ₂	461.00	S-Cl-Zn	-
165	(N-S-Cl) ₂	617.20	S-N	2.193
242	$S_3N_3Cl_3$ (M-2)	728.6	S-N	3.056
409	$S_3N_3Cl_3-ZnO-N-S-N$ (M-1)	1142.9	N-S-Cl	5.903
424	$S_3N_3Cl_3-Zn-(N-S)_2$ (M-1)	1617.4	N-S-Cl	12.625
460	$S_3N_3Cl_3 + (S-Cl)_3-N$ (M-1)	2079.1	N-S-Cl	19.536
487	$(S_3N_3Cl_3)$ (M-2)	2400.0	$\delta N-H$	33.157
570	$(S_3N_3Cl_3)-ZnO$ (M-3)	3124.5	$\delta N-H$	56.198
605	$(S_3N_3Cl_3)-ZnO-Cl$	3878.6	$\delta N-H$	86.598

electrons ($n = 1.70 \times 10^5$) express good conductivity of the complex.

A broad peak of high intensity was found in the EPR spectrum of the complex, suggesting its paramagnetic character, which is supported by the values of μ_{eff} (1.1136 B.M.) and magnetic susceptibility χ_A (0.0517×10^{-3}). The number of unpaired electrons, determined, are two, correspond-

Fig. 1. Proposed structure of the complex, $[S_3N_3Cl_3]_3.ZnO$.

ing bivalent zinc. The values of g_{\parallel} (1.62), g_{\perp} (1.68) and g_{av} (1.65) are according empty d energy shells to accept the electron pairs and to form coordinate bond with complex. Generally zinc complexes exhibit diamagnetism and $S_3N_3Cl_3$ is also diamagnetic in nature. Therefore the complex of $S_3N_3Cl_3$ with ZnO should be diamagnetic in character, which is not found experimentally. The abnormal behaviour of the Zn atom in the complex may be due to $4sp^3$ hybridisation as expressed below.

Zn^{2+} , during complex formation, received six electrons from three Cl-atoms of three $S_3N_3Cl_3$ rings. Due to the surrounded high electron repulsion, the electrons of $4s^1$ and $4p^1$ have paired as shown below and six electrons have been occupied by three vacant $4sp^3$ hybrid orbitals.

Hence the distorted tetrahedral structure of the complex as suggested by electronic spectrum is inferred and expressed by Fig. 1.

Experimental

$S_3N_3Cl_3$ prepared by Nelson and Heal's⁷ method by the chlorination of S_4N_4 ⁸ dissolved in CS_2 , kept in ice bath. The sky blue coloured product, formed, was separated, washed with cold CS_2 followed by ether, dried and confirmed by its melting point (168°). The complex was synthesised by refluxing a mixture of $S_3N_3Cl_3$ (1.0 g) and ZnO (0.5 g) in DMF solution for 24 h. The cream coloured mass, produced, was separated, washed with DMF, ice cold water, ethanol and ether successively dried and stored over fused $CaCl_2$ in a vacuum desiccator.

The estimations of the constituent elements of the complex were done gravimetrically as well as mass spectrometrically, recorded, on a Jeol SX 102/DA-6000, mass spectrometer. IR, electronic and EPR spectra of the complex were graphed on 820/PC (KBr), Perkin Elmer Lambda-15 (200–800 nm) and Varian F-109 X band (3400–5000 G) spectrometers respectively.

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